

Developing a framework for using authentic task-based listening materials for the 21st century learners

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Abstract – *This study proposes a framework, wherein the approaches on authentic and task-based learning are rooted. This framework emerged from the previous needs assessment conducted by the researcher, which will then serve as a blueprint for the development of the resource material on listening. Having reviewed a range of published researches about authentic task-based listening, the researcher was able to develop a framework, which is classified into modules indicating the given task, the language used, and the suggested lessons. In this framework, it is evident how many simple and natural tasks can be considered which exhibit a high degree of authenticity, not only in terms of task, but also in terms of communicative learning. Although most of the real world experiences can be achieved outside the classroom, it can be concluded that in academic settings, it is possible to simulate the real world in classrooms via presenting authentic task-based listening materials that are probable in occurring outside the safe classroom context and in learners' future vocational setting. The researcher suggests that other teachers also take the role of material developers and consider the benefits inherent in developing a framework for developing the listening skills of the 21st century learners.*

Keywords: Framework, authentic task-based listening materials, 21st century learners.

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Introduction

Listening has a significant role in daily communication and educational process. Various studies show the importance of listening as a communication skill. According to Adler et al., (2017), adults spend an average of 70% of their time gained in some sort of communication; of this an average of 45% is spent on listening compared to 30% speaking, 16% reading and 9% writing. Since listening holds such a large percentage of people's communication time, it is therefore advantageous to have effective listening abilities in order to handle daily listening needs.

Listening ability is important in the development of other language arts skills in a language classroom. When students are learning a language for the first time, they must usually listen to the words numerous times before they can recognize and pronounce correctly. Listening can also help students expand their vocabulary, develop their language proficiency, and improve their language usage (Barker, 1971). Cayer et al. (1971) find that the ability of students to comprehend written content through reading as well as express themselves through speaking and written communication is directly related to their language maturity in the listening phase. Dunkel (1991) also asserts that the key to obtaining proficiency in speaking is to enhance your listening comprehension skills. Listening skills are not only the foundation for the development of all other

abilities, but they are also the primary means by which students come into contact with the target language and culture (Curtain & Pesola, 1988).

Despite the importance of listening practice in language instruction, it is indeed ironic to note that listening is the skill being least being developed in formal education. In many countries, English language classes still emphasize only reading and writing skills. This is especially true in an English-as-a-foreign-language (EFL) environment, in which the English language is taught as a subject at school and only utilized inside the classroom, not outside.

Gegrewold (2011) conducted study on teachers and students' attitudes towards using authentic materials in EFL classes and concluded that although listening skill is one of the most important skills, the materials presented in course books for teaching listening skills are limited students to practice. She added that the listening texts in the teachers' guides are also not of various kinds through role plays, stories, jokes, and conversations are also recommended to be included as listening texts. Besides this, Bekena (2011) conducted a study on practices and challenges of teaching listening skills at Addis Ababa and Debrezeit peacekeeping English project centers and concluded that although materials like media in English, movies and songs have paramount importance to improve listening skills, they are not employed in teaching listening skills.

Few years ago, the researcher conducted a needs assessment with college students, and identified listening as the macro skill which students need to develop most. To address the need of developing the listening skills of the students, a resource material in listening is supposed to be utilized or developed. However, most of the listening materials being produced by the teachers are traditional and does not really prepare the students in the sense of real listening. Based from a firsthand experience, the researcher observes that most teachers rarely integrate activities, which aims to develop the students' listening skills. Students were usually asked to listen for the sole purpose of answering multiple choice questions, or to repeat after what the teacher said. But where in the real world is it being done?

Most students are less proficient in listening and it maybe because they are not being prepared to the real world that they will be facing soon after they graduated in school. Because language classroom discourse does not represent the language of the real world, students frequently have difficulty understanding people outside of the classroom (Paulston & Bruder, 1976; Porter & Roberts, 1981; Rings, 1986; Robinett, 1978). As Peachey (2011) explains, teachers should consider the fact that the moment students step outside the classroom, students have no control over the language they may hear or need to respond to. They are being surrounded by an immense spontaneous and unpredictable language. This is why, in many cases, even advanced pupils who succeed in the classroom struggle to cope when confronted with a real-life situation. They might simply have not taught in a way that will help them cope with this. If the goal of an English as a second language (ESL) program is "to prepare our students to cope with English outside the classroom" (Hafernik & Surguine, 1979), it is suggested that teachers are encouraged to employ listening materials that include samples of natural language from a variety of sources so that students are exposed to a wide range of themes, settings, and speakers (Nagle & Sanders, 1986; Paulston & Bruder, 1976). This can be achieved in the language classroom through the use of aural authentic materials. Furthermore, Gilman and Moody (1984) recommend that the teacher should use authentic materials when teaching advanced listening comprehension to students even at the beginning and intermediate levels.

This aspect that has been neglected in preparation of a listening material is called authenticity. The idea of authenticity was also at the heart of communicative language teaching. According to Swarbrick (1994), “authenticity” has been one of the essential concepts of communicative movement in language teaching from the beginning. This was attributed that communicative language instruction no longer used strictly structural approaches to language learning, but instead advocated the use of authentic texts made for a genuine communicative goal, among other reasons.

Authenticity is a crucial consideration when selecting appropriate listening materials for second-language students. Students must be prepared for real listening in the classroom, and aural authentic texts will expose students to real language from the start of their language studies (Bacon, 1989; Morton, 1999). However, in order to ensure transfer to real-life conversational situations, the teacher must provide language material with authentic native accents and intonation delivered at a rate of utterance that is typical of native speakers of the language (Grittner, 1980). Students who work with authentic materials will acquire significant practice in the skill of analyzing live speech without necessarily knowing every word of structure; as a result, they will improve their listening comprehension (Herron & Seay, 1991).

Results of the study conducted by Herron and Seay (1991) show that listening comprehension in language students enhances with increased exposure to authentic materials. If students are to use the language to communicate effectively in the real world, Rogers and Medley (1988) propose that students must learn the language in the context of real-life dialogue among native speakers.

Morrison (1989) also believes that authentic listening materials can and should be used at all levels, from beginner to advanced. Because actual language is the medium of everyday conversation, even beginning students require exposure to it (Oxford, Lavine, & Crookall, 1989; Porter & Roberts, 1981; Scarcella & Oxford, 1992). According to Herron and Seay (1991), in order to engage students in activities that resemble real-life listening, teachers should use more authentic texts at all levels of language education.

To distinguish authentic listening materials from non-authentic, Underwood (1989) identifies the following characteristic features. These are presented in the table below.

Table 1. Characteristic features of authentic and non-authentic listening text

Authentic listening text	Non-authentic listening text
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Natural rhythm • Natural intonation • Natural pronunciation (i.e. not especially carefully enunciated) • Some overlap between speakers (including interruption) • Normal rate of delivery (sometimes fast, sometimes slow) • Relatively unstructured language, which is used spontaneously in speech • Incomplete sentences, false starts, hesitations • Background noise and, sometimes background voices • Natural starts and stops • Less densely packed information than in written language 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unnatural rhythm • Unnatural intonation • Over-clear enunciation • Little overlap between speakers • Slow (and perhaps monotonous) delivery • Structured language which was meant to be read silently rather than spoken aloud • Complete sentences as utterances • No background noise • Artificial stops and starts • Densely packed information

Another feature of instructional material design that many major language scholars now consider crucial is that it encourages task-based learning. The term 'task' is used to describe two types of activities. The first kind of task, as Nunan (2004) states, is related to real world and is called “target task”, and the second category is “pedagogical task”. Pedagogical tasks are done in the classroom, while target tasks are completed outside of the classroom for authentic users.

Richards and Rodgers (1986) defines pedagogical task as:

“...an activity or action which is carried out as the result of processing or understanding language (i.e. as a response). For example, drawing a map while listening to a tape, listening to an instruction and performing a command may be referred to as tasks (as cited in Nunan, 2004, p. 2).”

Unlike traditional and conventional activities, which are designed from a pedagogical viewpoint and often overlook authenticity and real-life situations (Izadpanah, 2010), a task-based approach deals more directly with real and online communication by providing classroom listening experiences that are similar to the demands of authentic language use (Newton & Nation, 2008). Task-based activities, by facilitating the use of language in meaningful contexts, can have a significant impact on the learning process.

A task-based approach to instruction in L2 listening actively engages learners in the listening process by giving them a specific task or focus that clearly indicates the objective for learning, as well as encouraging student reflection and evaluation of their progress during and after task completion. According to Field (2008), the goal of a task-based listening method is to teach students how to employ strategies throughout the listening process. A task-based approach to listening education is more student-centered than other approaches. Students learn and practice a 'macro-strategy,' which is an approach that may be used in a number of situations when listening to different materials. Students are empowered to examine their own comprehension as they discover problem areas of understanding and then check and clarify their understandings using both the listening material and possibly their peers.

Prabhu (1990) developed has three main models for task-based language teaching: pre-task (commonly called a preparatory activity), task cycle (meaning focused activity or interactive process action), and post task (an activity for attending to form). Teachers have a variety of perspectives and understandings when it comes to creating assignments for classroom activities. Even when they provide task-based activities, they fail to portray the critical processes and procedures that are at the heart of the task's primary meaning. As a result, they focus significantly more on the discrete language skills and functions that must be learned throughout task-activities.

Motallebzadeh (2013) investigated the effect of task-based listening activities on listening comprehension self-efficacy of Iranian intermediate EFL learners. During nineteen (19) sessions, the experimental group was treated through task-based listening activities, including different kinds of listening tasks such as ordering, filling the gaps, multiple choice, and interactive activities. The results revealed that the experimental group, which was given task-based listening exercises, benefited greatly from the treatment. It was determined that task-based listening activities increase the development of learners' listening self-efficacy, and that this method is better to the traditional method of teaching listening, which consists solely of asking and responding questions.

Schweppe (2012) explores the academic listening skills of secondary ELs to see if a task-based approach to L2 listening teaching combined with explicit training in meta-cognitive methods improves ELs' listening comprehension of science information and allows them to do tangible tasks while listening. The findings of this study confirm results (Field, 2008; Hinkel, 2006; Vandergrift, 2007) that integrated models such as content- and task-based instruction greatly affect student learning. Students were more attentive and continued to listen to what they heard even when they did not understand it because of the accountability involved with task-based listening. Schweppe also gives a criterion for academic task-based listening.

Table 2. Academic task-based listening (Schweppe, 2012)

Design Feature	Description
Goal	The listening task must serve to develop student comprehension and promote note-taking skills.
Input	The input includes the listening material (e.g., lecture, recording, YouTube video etc.) and any non-verbal supports (e.g., graphic organizers) used to help process input.
Conditions	The listening task is non-reciprocal and the note-taking process can be either guided or unguided.
Procedures	The note-taking process can occur during and/or after listening and should encourage students to write down topics, insert diagrams to help them retain input, or note main ideas and supporting details or examples.
Predicted Outcomes: Product and Process	The outcome should document that students were able to generate a set of notes that provide a written record of the listening content.

To determine what needs to be done to prepare students for real-world settings, Joiner et al. (1989) suggested that teachers evaluate existing procedures and materials used in language classrooms to determine what students listen to, how much they listen to, and how they listen to examples of natural or actual language in the classroom

It is true that a number of significant studies on how to develop the listening skills of the students have been done recently, but the question of how this listening material should be

developed, especially the application of **authenticity** and **task-based** approach has rarely been considered. In response to this challenge, the researcher will develop a listening material to get beyond the limitations of a given text or lesson. This material will feature two major aspects of listening materials: being **authentic** and **task-based**, as Oura (2001) believes, may add to the overall effectiveness of the learning process because the learner sees the activity as relevant to his or her learning needs.

However, prior to material preparation, a practical framework in using authentic task-based listening material is developed. The framework emerged out of the previous research conducted by the researcher, which will then serve as a blueprint for the development of the listening material.

The proposed framework is significant because it is anchored in the K to 12 curricula. First, two of the language teaching principles in the component of language learning process of the curriculum reflect the approach of authentic learning. These principles are:

- **Interaction:** Language learning will take place in the context of communication (oral and written). Students will engage in activities that imitate real-life scenarios with various language demands (purposes, themes, and audiences) to strengthen their socialization skills.
- **Contextualization:** Learners will be given tasks and exercises to complete to acquire the language in authentic and meaningful contexts. For example, lessons will be structured around learning outcomes, a subject, or a certain type of text to assist students employ associated language skills, grammatical items/structures, and vocabulary effectively in spoken and written language to suit the purpose, audience, context, and culture. Explicit instruction and accompanying follow-up practice will reinforce learning points.

Second, the K to 12 program aims to produce Filipino graduates, who are holistically developed with 21st century skills such as Information, Media and Technology skills, Learning and Innovation skills, Effective Communication skills, and Life and Career skills. The study aims to develop the students' listening proficiency, which is one of the communication skills. Since effective communication skill is one of the 21st century skills, thus the proposed framework is geared towards the success of the 21st century learners.

Chou (2017) in his study "*A Task-based Language Teaching Approach to Developing Metacognitive Strategies for Listening Comprehension*", he developed a framework as a strategy awareness in language learning. It aimed to see how well a task-based teaching framework could help intermediate Chinese EFL university students build metacognitive awareness of listening comprehension. A total of 88 sophomores participated in the study, which was conducted in a quasi-experimental design. For 18 weeks, the experimental group received task-based listening instruction with embedded strategies, while the control group received solely strategy-based teaching. In the pretest and posttest stages, listening tests and questionnaires were used. Based on the findings, the experimental group improved their metacognitive awareness of listening strategies and outperformed the control group in the listening test. Tasks were viewed as an important channel of input improvement for increasing listening capacity by the students in the experimental group.

This framework is also significant for it could be readily extendable to other language classes like Filipino, which also integrates the development of listening as one of the communication skills. English and Filipino are the two main language classes in the Philippines, which both develop the different macro skills. Listening, because of its importance, should be given the most attention as an area of instruction, as well as an area of research in education. And this should be spearheaded by the language teachers, English and Filipino. This would empower them to incorporate the material in their teaching contexts to mitigate existing communication related challenges.

Herron and Seay (1991) believe that students can be directed to extract general and specific meaning from oral authentic texts while strengthening general listening-comprehension abilities with the right instructional framework from the teacher. Using authentic materials allows students to experience the benefits of learning a language early on in their studies. Melvin and Stout (1987) maintains that students who study with authentic materials develop an interest in the language as a result of what they have learned about what it can do for them. In the past, students exhibited good listening skills by accurately completing comprehension questions after the information was provided. Nowadays, students are more likely to be expected to do a task while listening and/or a follow-up activity that requires them to apply information from the course in real-world situations (Joiner, 1991). Lund (1990) even suggests that classroom listening teaching and practice be brought as close to real-world listening as possible.

Hence, this paper presents the development of a framework, wherein the approaches on authentic and task-based learning is rooted. These approaches delineate methods and techniques with the procedures through pre-listening, while-listening and post-listening.

Methods

Needs Assessment

From the needs assessment conducted by the researcher to the college students, it was identified that among the four macro skills in English, Listening is the skill that students need to develop most. The assessment was done to address the needs, or ‘gaps’ between the current conditions and desired conditions, for the development of the listening proficiency of the 21st century learners in the Philippines.

Development of Framework

At this stage, the researcher developed a framework according to the identified need of developing the listening proficiency of the 21st century learners. To ensure that the framework will be actually used as needed, it is anchored to the significant approaches and principles contained within the listening material.

Selection of Approaches

A. Authentic Listening

Authentic listening is an instructional approach that allows students to investigate, discuss, and meaningfully build concepts and relationships in situations that incorporate real-world problems and projects. The basic idea is that if what students are learning mirrors real-life contexts, equips them with practical and useful skills, and addresses topics that are relevant and applicable to their lives outside of school, they will be more interested in what they are learning, more motivated to learn new concepts and skills, and better prepared to succeed in college, careers, and adulthood.

B. Task-based Listening

Task-based listening is an approach to listening by understanding orally delivered information. Students are required to listen to what to what are described as “authentic” situations and to “do something” with the information. The explicit nature of task-based listening, as well as the repetition associated with task specialization, could explain the development in individual knowledge. Furthermore, task-based listening allows teachers to identify particular areas for improvement while evaluating student progress.

Results

The Framework

Having reviewed a range of published researches about authentic task-based listening, the researcher was able to develop a framework to address need of developing the listening proficiency of the 21st century learners.

Table 3. Module 1: Direct Purposeful Experience

Task	Language	Suggested Lesson/Situation
1. Listening to an Advertisement	Advertisement	Idiomatic Expression
2. Listening to a Plane Announcement	Safety Guidelines	Parallelism
3. Listening to a TV News Program	News	Wh Questions, Identifying the Main idea
4. Listening to a Tour Guide in a Field Trip	Tour guidelines	Following Directions
5. Podcasting	Song	Figures of Speech

Table 4. Module 2: Information Gap

Task	Language	Suggested Lesson/Situation
1. Listening to a Call Center Agent for: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Booking a flight • Asking for a customer service • Shopping 	Telephone Conversation	Expressions in a Telephone Conversation, Communication process
2: Asking/Looking for a Destination	Directions	Prepositions of Place
3: Counselling	Given advice	Identifying the Main Idea
4: Drawing/Sketching one’s Description of person, place or thing	Description	Adjectives
5: Spot the Difference Game	Mechanics	Tag Questions, Yes-No Questions, Verbs

Table 5. Module 3: Interactive Simulation

Task	Language	Suggested Lesson/Situation
1: Listening to an organization’s advocacy	Advocacy Orientation	Essay/Research Writing, Communication skills
2: Interview	Interview questions / answers	Tag Questions, Yes-No Questions, Verbs
3: Meeting	Minutes of the meeting	Writing minutes, business plan
4: Mock Election	Language in an election process	Coherence, Unity, Filling-up information sheet, vocabulary
5: Conversation, Eavesdropping, Passing a Message	Conversation	Communication Skills (listening for details, turn-taking, re-telling, backchanneling, negotiating meaning, recognizing stages, shifting topic, exploiting ambiguity)

Table 6. Module 4: Contrived Experiences

Task	Language	Suggested Lesson/Situation
1. Cooking Demonstration	Cooking procedure	Action Verbs, Transitional Devices
2. Product Demonstration	Product instruction	Action Verbs, Transitional Devices
3. Zumba/Work out Program	Zumba/Work out instruction	Action Verbs, Transitional Devices
4. Listening to a Lecture	Lecture	Listening comprehension
5. Storytelling, Listening to a story	Anecdote, Fictional Stories	Elements of a story, Narrative Essay

Table 7. Module 5: Recorded Authentic Material

Task	Language	Suggested Lesson/Situation
1: Weather Forecast	Weather Forecast	Process: Rhetoric Device
2: Inaugural Speech	Inaugural Speech	Persuasive Essay
3: School Announcement	School Announcement	Noting Details
4: Terminal Announcement	Terminal Announcement	Nouns
5: IELTS Listening Test	Conversation	Main Idea

Use of the Framework

The framework is designed as a proposed listening material to be used for language classes, which is supposed to develop listening as one of the macro skills. Having identified and incorporated the necessary elements of an authentic task-based listening material into the framework, it can now be put to use. Uses may include:

- **Planning** – clarifies the initiative or program's strategies, identifies targets and outcomes, prepare a grant proposal, identifies necessary partnerships, and estimates timelines and needed resources for the effort.
- **Designing the Listening material** – designs a material to incorporate the significant elements of an authentic task-based listening material.
- **Implementation** – determines the elements that the teacher has and do not have in the initiative or program, develops a management plan, and makes mid-course adjustments.
- **Communication and advocacy** – justifies to others why the program will work and explains how investments will be used.
- **Evaluation** – documents accomplishments, identifies differences between the ideal program and the currently operating one, determines which indicators will be used to measure success and frames questions about attribution (of cause and effect) and contribution of the program to the mission.

Discussion

This framework attempts to outline the design of the authentic task-based listening material. It is classified into five modules, where each targets practice of real life situations.

Module 1 is Direct Purposeful Experiences. As the bottom level in Dale's cone of experience (1960), it represents reality or the closest things to real, everyday life. Direct experiences are essentially what the students can learn by doing it because the activities allow the learners to use all senses. According to Dale, the more sensory channels available for interacting with a material, the more students will be able to benefit from it. Because experience is the best teacher, this method of teaching is known to be the most effective means of instructing students. The activities can be listening to a plane announcement, tour guide in a field trip, TV news program, advertisement, and a music from podcast.

Module 2 is Contrived experiences. This is the second to the bottom of Dale's cone of experience (1960). They are the ones that require a lot of participation and simulate real-life events or activities. Contrived Experiences is used in the absence of direct experiences as materials for

instruction. We make use of this contrived materials to overcome limitations of space and time, to edit reality for us to be able to focus on parts or a process of a system that we intend to study to overcome difficulties of size to understand the inaccessible, to help the learners understand abstractions. While we utilize simulations and games to make lectures more interactive and to help students build decision-making and knowledge creation skills, we use representative models or mock-ups of reality in this case for practical reasons. It can be in a form of a lecture, listening to recorded materials, or storytelling. Contrived experiences can be demonstrations of cooking, dancing, exercising or listening to a lecture storyteller.

Module 3 is Information Gap. An information-gap task is a language teaching strategy in which students are missing information needed to accomplish a task or solve a problem and must communicate with their peers to fill in the gaps (Larsen-Freeman & Anderson, 2011). She claims that it is frequently employed in communicative language instruction and task-based language acquisition. To solve a problem or finish a task, students must communicate with one another. Individual students do not have all of the information needed to complete these activities, resulting in a "gap" that can only be filled by conversing with other students and exchanging information. The missing information required to complete the activity can be in a form of directions, consultation or even games. Some examples of information gap are listening to call center agent when one needs to book for a flight, ask for a customer service or shop; when one needs to look for a destination, need for an advice, sometimes one needs to draw or sketch a description like the cartographic sketch, or sometimes when one just needs to be entertained in a form of games.

Module 4 is Interactive Simulation. Oura (2001) gives examples of classroom activities in which students use authentic resources and have defined tasks to complete in order to meet real-world language objectives. Interactive simulation is an approach, which is to simulate various real-world settings in which students engage with authentic materials to familiarize themselves with the details. Students must then take on a certain role in the scenario and communicate with other students in a realistic manner while attempting to complete specific tasks. It can be in a form of conducting a mock-up interview, meeting, election, listening to an organization's advocacy or simply a real class conversation. In the real world, most students will probably not join any organization, be interviewed or attend a meeting. However, this activity provides the opportunity for students to develop the real world ability to answer questions on the spot, as well as to converse with any person they will come in contact with.

Module 5 is Recorded Authentic Material. These are materials which can be used in case the time and resources in facilitating the activities in Modules 1 to 4 would not be available. These audio materials are recorded in a DVD, which is embedded in the instructional material to be developed. The materials can also be considered as authentic as they reflect characteristics of an authentic listening material such as background noise, and others. The advantage of using the recorded audio materials is that the learner would have the chance to play each of the recordings more than once. From a cognitive perspective, they believe that L2 listeners should be exposed to a variety of diverse listening events and should listen to them regularly and repeatedly. Learners should listen to as many different types of authentic texts as possible, covering a wide range of themes and topics, according to the principle of variety (Vandergrift & Goh, 2012). The idea is concerned with the cognitive advantage of repetition. Learners can acquire familiar with the content, terminology, and structure of a spoken text by listening to it multiple times. Learners can verify the information they have received and focus on new points in the text with each repetition.

Other authentic activities that can be recorded are weather forecast, inaugural speech, school announcement, terminal announcement and a court proceeding. Each activity would have a suggested lesson, where each lesson is divided into pre-listening, during listening and post listening.

The classification of the framework in three columns supports Breen (1987), who proposed three authenticity types, such that of task, language and situation. It also adapted the suggestions given by Peachey (2011) that link types of text to possible tasks. It is reflected that the listening material should as much as possible resembles the original purpose for which the text was intended, as Peachey puts it, “authentic materials”. For example, if a person listens to someone giving directions, the person does so in order to be able to find a destination. When developing a listening material, this is what should be considered when setting tasks for students. Instead of just getting a score, the purpose should describe the work assigned to pupils, allowing them to enhance their capacities to interpret and process what they hear.

All of these classroom activities, which make use of authentic listening materials and assign students particular tasks to accomplish in order to complete a project, can provide students with a very meaningful experience. During such activities, students would undoubtedly gain more confidence in their ability to use the language. By emphasizing on practical language skills, it provides a means to bring real-world experiences into the classroom.

Conclusion

In conclusion, because one of the goals of classroom listening is to prepare students for real-life listening outside of the classroom, authentic task-based aural materials must be used at all levels of language instruction and listening comprehension training.

In this framework, it is evident how many simple and natural tasks can be considered which exhibit a high degree of authenticity, not only in terms of task, but also in terms of communicative learning. Supported by the significant approaches of authentic and task based learning, coupled with the characteristic features of authenticity promoted by Underwood (1989), the researcher believes this framework, which is a basis for developing the listening material, will be more effective in motivating the students to develop their listening proficiency and communicate properly in real-world contexts.

Considering the needs of the 21st century learners in the context, this framework recognizes the social media platforms as their way to communicate with the outside world. This generation, as described in the K to 12 Basic Education Curriculum (2016), is regarded as being creative and collaborative and will have a great impact on the way companies work when they join the workforce.

In this framework the best authentic task-based listening activity is by engaging students to come up with an advocacy collateral that shall approximately show students’ ability to listen and use the English language accurately and appropriately. Students need to join any organizations or group and support their advocacy by designing a community or school-based advocacy material that shall benefit its immediate constituents. However, the least authentic would be the recorded authentic listening materials, like a weather forecast, inaugural speech, school announcement, terminal announcement and a court proceeding. These activities may have no authentic

environment and does not directly deal with authentic participants, but these activities provide the opportunity for students to develop the real world ability by listening intensively to answer questions on the spot, accordingly and confidently. Generally, all of these listening activities, utilizing authentic and task-based materials can be a very meaningful experience for students. By emphasizing on practical language skills, it provides a means to bring real-world experiences into the classroom.

Although most of the real world experiences can be achieved outside the classroom, it can be concluded that in academic settings it is possible to simulate the real world in classrooms by delivering actual task-based listening materials that are likely to occur outside of the safe school context and in learners' future occupational setting. Also, the researcher, like other language teachers who as literature suggests also take the role of material developers may consider the benefits inherent in developing this framework. The listening material that can be produced from this framework can be used in creating a connection between the language learners' needs and the real world outside the instructional context.

This framework for listening development could be implemented to any listening text. This, however, is not the only way to enhance the students' listening proficiency or to create a listening lesson. There are more authentic task-based listening activities that can also be considered. The next phase of this process will be to develop indicators that can be used to validate the framework needed for the design of the listening material.

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